

A Case of Congenitally Corrected Transposition of the Great Arteries at Age 75 Years

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ABSTRACT/INTRODUCTION

Congenitally Corrected Transposition of the Great Arteries (CCTGA) is a rare congenital disorder that accounts for less than 1% (~ 0.5%) of all congenital heart malformations.^[1] It is described as “double discordance” because both the atrioventricular and ventriculo-arterial connections are inappropriate.^[2] CCTGA is usually associated with other abnormalities, including conduction system defects and anatomic anomalies, such as ventricular septal defect (VSD), pulmonary stenosis (PS) and tricuspid valve malformations.^[1,2] The clinical presentation depends on the presence or absence of these associated entities.^[2] The natural history is mainly dictated by the function of the systemic right ventricle and tricuspid valve as well as the existence of concomitant arrhythmias, especially complete heart block.^[3] The management of CCTGA remains a serious challenge and depends on the age of the patient, the symptoms and the accompanying defects.^[4]

Keywords: Congenitally Corrected Transposition; Ventricular septal defect; Pulmonary stenosis

CASE PRESENTATION

A 75-year-old female patient with a clear past medical record, active farm worker, no smoker, presented to the emergency department with dyspnoea on moderate exertion since 1 month. She was afebrile, hemodynamically stable, not tachycardic, with no signs of peripheral oedema or pulmonary congestion and normal JVP. Her blood analysis was unremarkable, as well as the ABGs (SaO₂ 94% in FiO₂ 21%). The pre-test probability for Pulmonary Embolism was low, therefore, no further investigation occurred. The chest X-ray revealed a dextrocardia and then a cardiologist’s consultation was asked. The 12-lead surface ECG (**Image 1**) revealed Sinus Rhythm, q waves in leads II, aVF, V1, V3, poor R-wave progression in precordial leads and fragmented QRS, with QRS duration 80msec. The bedside echocardiogram raised the suspicion of CCTGA as the “systemic” ventricle appeared to have more trabeculae than the “pulmonic” ventricle, with no other obvious cardiac abnormalities. A CMR was further ordered, establishing the diagnosis of CCTGA in a patient with situs solitus dextrocardia and no other congenital defects (**Image 2**). The patient was then admitted to the ward and

further investigated with 24h ambulatory Holter monitoring which did not reveal any arrhythmias or conduction delays. Moreover, the patient performed an Exercise Treadmill Test with modified Bruce protocol that uncovered hypertensive response during the peak of exercise (BP 185/91mmHg, Exercise time 8' 35'') and a Coronary Arteries Catheterization with no obstructive disease. The patient was released with ACEi, b-blocker, MRA, statin and Aspirin and was asked to have regular follow-up in the outpatient cardiology clinic.

DISCUSSION

CCTGA is a disorder that arises from an embryonic error during cardiac development at the third gestation week, when the primary heart tube turns leftward instead of to the right, leading to abnormal positioning of the ventricles.^[3] As a result, the morphologically left ventricle (LV) is connected through the mitral valve to the right atrium (RA) and supplies the pulmonary artery and thus the pulmonary circulation, while the morphologically right ventricle (RV) is connected through the tricuspid valve to left atrium (LA) and supplies the aorta and consequently the systemic circulation.^[2] These abnormal connections co-exist in around 20% of patients with cardiac malposition, especially dextrocardia, as in our patient, leading to an even more complex anatomical presentation.^[5]

CCTGA is, in most cases, associated with other structural deformities, including VSDs which are usually perimembranous, PS which is frequently fibromuscular and tricuspid valve anomalies, with Ebstein-like malformations accounting for a significant proportion of them.^[6] Conduction defects are also common, due to the abnormal position and course of AV node and bundle of His.^[6] The presence or absence of these lesions determines the clinical manifestation of the disease.^[2] Patients with accompanied abnormalities develop symptoms in infancy or early childhood, while those without can remain asymptomatic until late adulthood.^[1,2] Our patient has isolated CCTGA, that accounts for 1-9% of all CCTGA cases^[3] and she was asymptomatic until the age of 75 years, although she mentioned some episodes of dyspnoea throughout the years during rigorous efforts.

The long-term outcome is mainly affected by 2 major problems, complete AV block that can lead to sudden cardiac death and inability of the RV to function effectively as a systemic pump that can induce congestive heart failure.^[7] One-third of patients with CCTGA develop complete heart block, which can be either present at birth or develop later in life with the risk being increased by 2% per year.^[3] The probability of systemic ventricular impairment rises with age and by the fifth decade of life one one-third of patients with isolated CCTGA and more than 50% of the patients with associated lesions have moderate to severe RV dysfunction.^[7] This is mainly attributed to the hypertrophy of the RV and the coronary artery insufficiency which results in inadequate perfusion of the RV wall.^[1,8] Moreover, studies have shown that the RV function is reduced during exercise^[9] and can be adversely affected during pregnancy.^[11] Surprisingly, our patient reached the age of 75 without any of the aforementioned problems, although she was a farmer worker with strenuous everyday activities and had undergone 3 uneventful pregnancies in her life. Our case suggests that the natural history of a patient with CCTGA and no other additional congenital defects might be similar to that of a normal individual, as another case report of an 88-year old male with first diagnosis of CCTGA has implemented.^[10]

The choice of an appropriate therapeutic strategy for patients with CCTGA is laborious. The selection is based on the age and presentation of patient at diagnosis as well as the co-existence of other anomalies.^[4] CCTGA is not itself an indication for surgery, which is commonly preferred in symptomatic young patients, usually < 15 years of age.^[8] The major challenge remains the management of that specific sub-group of patients with congestive heart failure since the data available are scanty.^[8] As a result, the basic pharmacological principles for congestive heart failure with RASS inhibitors, MRAs, beta blockers and diuretics if needed, are usually followed^[11], as we did in this case. Data for SGLT2i are unavailable.

CONCLUSION

CCTGA is a rare and complex disease that demonstrates a diverse clinical course largely dictated by the presence and severity of accompanied defects. Most patients develop progressive RV dysfunction by the age of 45, however, here we presented a case of a woman with isolated CCTGA who, despite her encumbered medical history and lifestyle, managed to reach the eighth decade of life before she developed heart failure symptoms. Unfortunately, there are limited evidence-based management options for adult patients with CCTGA and systemic RV impairment and thus further studies for the discovery of effective curative solutions are of great importance.

Image 1: 12-lead surface ECG

Image 2: Cardiac Magnetic Resonance

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